

PROBLEMS OF INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF YOUTH STUDENTS IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. Student youth is a visible and active social layer of society. A large number of young people are students at universities and colleges in our republic. At the same time, as an active social stratum, they are a group full of energy, striving for the future despite all difficulties, trying to make full use of their opportunities. All this is a characteristic feature of the character of young students and is a factor that allows them to become a real active part of society.

Keywords: social protection of students, increasing students' confidence in the future, explaining to students about political, economic and social reforms.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ В СИСТЕМЕ НЕПРЕРЫВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. Студенческая молодежь является видимой и активной социальной прослойкой общества. Большое количество молодежи обучается в вузах и колледжах нашей республики. В то же время как активный социальный слой они представляют собой группу, полную энергии, устремленную в будущее, несмотря на все трудности, стремящуюся в полной мере использовать свои возможности. Все это является характерной чертой характера студенческой молодежи и является фактором, позволяющим им стать реальной активной частью общества.

Ключевые слова: социальная защита студентов, повышение уверенности студентов в завтрашнем дне, разъяснение студентам политических, экономических и социальных реформ.

INTRODUCTION

Every student who graduates from high school first of all thinks about his future profession and who he will work as, what kind of specialty he will take in the future always worries him. Fulfilling the dreams of young students about the profession means protecting their rights in this field. The results of the research show that the following practical works should be carried out in order to further improve the social mood of students:

- development of an event in each department in order to first of all ensure the love and trust of students towards their majors;
- to create measures to raise the level of teaching in our university to the level of modern requirements, taking into account the wishes of students;
- to increase students' confidence in the future, to determine their perspective and to determine specific measures in the dean's office and departments to help them;
- creation of measures to further improve library work;
- creation and implementation of the student social protection program;
- creation and implementation of measures to ensure better teaching of foreign language and computer technology to students;

- to take measures to eliminate vices such as localism, bribery, lying, and rudeness among teachers and students, which are considered factors that threaten security, and to do practical work in this field;
- development of support measures for students to study at the master's degree and find a good job in the future;
- to take measures to further increase students' confidence that the future of Uzbekistan will be great;
- creation and introduction of a program to inform and promote students about the political, economic and social reforms taking place in Uzbekistan;
- in-depth study of the real reasons for getting involved in various ideological, political, and religious currents and developing measures to prevent it;
- creation of measures to increase the level of students' and teachers' use of mass media, especially the press;
- creating activities to help students earn extra money in their spare time;
- developing measures to create conditions for our students to study abroad;
- to see activities for studying and monitoring students' mood.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The development and implementation of social monitoring of higher educational institutions is an important tool for increasing the activity of professors and teachers.

Society is setting itself the task of forming a free person with independent thinking, political consciousness, and high culture. This means educating people who realize their value, have a strong will, complete faith, and have a clear goal in life.

Student youth is a visible and active social layer of society. A large number of young people are students at universities and colleges in our republic. At the same time, as an active social stratum, they are a group full of energy, striving for the future despite all difficulties, trying to make full use of their opportunities. All this is a characteristic feature of the character of young students and is a factor that allows them to become a real active part of society.

At the moment, taking into account their social situation, it should be noted that the student youth are not in the same socio-economic situation. Some students do not worry financially, while others try to find extra work to pay tuition fees and solve other personal problems, because of the different social and economic status of the family.

Today's students of Uzbekistan are multi-ethnic, they believe in different religions. This diversity, of course, strengthens the difference between their today's and tomorrow's life goals and interests. The importance of this diversity in the development of social and political activity of students is not very great. But here their influence is undoubtedly present. This is why it is inappropriate to evaluate the socio-political activity of young students unilaterally today.

Difficulties during the transition to the current market economy often do not leave time to participate in social and political movements or to be socially and politically active. From an economic point of view, socio-political activism may not bring material benefits to a person, but socio-political activism only requires a person to voluntarily demonstrate his civil-political rights and duties. People's lifestyles have changed, including the political consciousness of students, their worldview, and their assessment of political situations in society. During our scientific research, it was found that the socio-political activity of current students is at a low level. As a

result of the sociological survey conducted among students, we were convinced that the socio-political activity of young students is at a passive level today.

What is the reason for the shallowness and incoherence of students' opinions on the social and political events happening around us, on the world stage? The reason for this is that the level of political culture and political consciousness has not yet been fully formed.

It is known that in our country, with the honor of independence, all necessary political, legal, spiritual and ideological conditions are being created to make a person a direct active participant in the political and spiritual life of society and to raise the level of his political culture and political consciousness. In his speech at the 1st session of the 2nd convocation of the Oliy Majlis, President Islam Karimov emphasized the following points: "As people's political consciousness, political culture, and political activity increase, the state transfers its tasks to non-state structures and citizens themselves. It is necessary to hand it over to the management bodies step by step".

These thoughts of our head of state are directly aimed at solving the tasks of deepening the democratic reforms implemented in our country, forming the foundations of civil society. Improving the political and legal culture of the members of our society, increasing their political and social activity should become the main criteria of our democratic development today.

RESULTS

The results of a sociological survey conducted among university students showed that the first question "How do you rate the level of teaching at your university?" to the question, 50% of students marked it as "medium", 42% as "high", and 8% as low. "How difficult do you think the textbooks are?" 80.5% of students think it is average, 11% think it is easy, and 8.5% think it is difficult. 72% of the students participating in the survey stated that they are studying on the basis of a contract, and the remaining 28% of students are studying on the basis of a state grant. "Tell me, approximately what percentage of students both studying and working make up in your faculty?" to the question, 10% of students chose 40-50%, 20% chose 10-20%, 30% of students chose 30-40%, and 40% of students chose 20-30%. In order to learn the opinions of students studying at the university about the scientific potential of the teachers and senior teachers teaching them, the question "In your opinion, what is the level of scientific potential of the teachers and senior teachers teaching at your faculty?" the question was asked. 67.8% of students considered it "high", 15.2% "medium", 9% "low", and 3% students "very low". "Do you use the library?" was asked, and the answers to this question are as follows - 29% "when necessary", 31% "sometimes", 20% "never", 20% "always". "What would you suggest to improve the quality of education?" the question was answered as follows: "Lectures should be given only by experienced professors and associate professors" (21.1%); "It is necessary to increase the attention to the independent work of students" (9%); "Teachers of foreign universities should be invited to study abroad" (19.9%); "Teachers' qualifications should be constantly monitored" (37.5%).

As can be seen, 87.5% of students agreed with the proposals, but 12.5% of students expressed their opinion on this question.

Most of the suggestions were "increasing the use of innovative technologies in the course of classes" and, in addition, "lessons should be conducted in small groups".

Most of the participants in the survey (47.5%) said that they were happy to be studying at the university, and 27.2% were satisfied with their studies. 8% of the respondents said that they

were not satisfied with studying at the university. The obtained data show that most of our students (66.7%) like their chosen specialty. One in four respondents live in university dormitories. 15.6% of the participants in the study always use university catering facilities, and 61% sometimes. every four diners are satisfied with the quality of food, 40% said that they have no other option, and 17% said that they visit catering establishments only because the price of food is relatively satisfactory.

It is known that more and more students face problems during the educational process. Therefore, relying on their opinion to improve work in this regard can yield positive results. one out of every two students demanded that students should pay more attention to their independent work and increase laboratory work, and it has been practically proven that the university rector is acting in this direction. In particular, lectures make up 40% of the new curriculum, and practical training makes up 60%, which is a clear example of this.

DISCUSSION

The results of the conducted survey were statistically processed and a set of preliminary measures was created, and with their help, collective factors of quality improvement in the education system were recommended. These include:

- * radical reform of the education system, reorientation of existing educational institutions and creation of a social base for training specialists who can work in new conditions and modern technologies;

- * raising the quality of the educational process to the level of world standards, introducing completely new methods of education, modern pedagogical and information technologies;

- * improvement of structures of educational institutions, in particular, sharp development of entrepreneurship;

- * educating young people in the spirit of national pride, universal human values, patriotism, loyalty, love of science and work;

- * creating conditions for young people to receive modern professional education;

- * creation and development of personnel potential consisting of highly qualified specialists who can quickly solve all problems;

- * equipping the material and technical base of the educational system with new educational literature, modern equipment and communication-computer technology;

- * creation of necessary socio-economic conditions to increase respect for the teaching profession, increase interest in the work of teachers and teachers;

- * creation of socio-demographic structure of education system employees, its formation, dynamics and perspective;

- * ensuring that students, their potential, future demand for them and their level of knowledge are up-to-date;

- * studying the social status of students and their attitude to learning;

- * analyzing students' level of knowledge with the help of sociological research and taking measures to increase it to an alternative level;

- * formation of a scientific worldview in students, more involvement in scientific and research work;

- * ways to study students' health and improve their health;

* Determination of socio-economic problems of investment policy in the higher education system, etc.

CONCLUSIONS

To build a great future state similar to the ideas and ideology of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, that is, to build a prosperous and free Motherland, to form a free and free society, to educate a perfect human being, to create a highly cultured and spiritual society and a high-level. Considering that achieving material well-being is possible on the basis of modern knowledge and that this path is the only correct path, we are developing the educational system of our country based on a unique and appropriate model and its first swallow the results are endlessly pleasing to our people. Because every person has the right to learn according to the Constitution, that is, our dictionary, and the full implementation of this right is the main task of the education system. The implementation of such a task requires constant monitoring of the implementation process of the National Program and plans in the educational system. After all, it is impossible to ensure the effective development of the educational system without information and without analyzing its changes and quickly correcting the negative situations encountered in life. A timely solution to this issue requires the creation of a separate management mechanism, that is, a monitoring system, in the educational system.

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